

INTEGRATION OF SCIENCE SUBJECTS INTO LANGUAGE LEARNING TO BOOST LANGUAGE SKILLS

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Annotation.

The article is devoted to the technology of subject-language integrated learning (Content and Language Integrated Learning) as an innovative method of teaching a foreign language at a university. A modern highly qualified specialist should have communication skills in a foreign language and be able to carry out communication in the professional sphere. Therefore, the conditions of modern life required the introduction of integrated approaches to the higher education system in order to train specialists in the field of economics, business and other branches of professional activity capable of to use a foreign language as a tool of professional activity in solving complex tasks. The article also discusses the methodological principles and features of the designated technology, the advantages of its implementation in higher education, as well as the difficulties that the academic staff of the university may face when implementing it. The paper examines the contradictions faced by teachers of a foreign language for professional purposes and teachers of specialized disciplines, and provides a critical assessment of how well curricula and programs meet the needs of teachers and students. The advantages and disadvantages of using the technology of subject-language integrated learning in the organization of classes in order to help teachers effectively plan their activities are also investigated. In conclusion, the author argues that an integrated interdisciplinary approach to teaching a foreign language and profile-oriented disciplines based on the described technology is a powerful platform necessary for the training of highly qualified specialists in a specific area of economics.

Keywords

subject-language integrated learning; interdisciplinarity; innovative methods; professional development; integration; professional training; English for professional purposes.

The system of higher education functions in the era of universal globalization and the rapid growth of relations that dictate the need to master a foreign language as a means of communication in the professional sphere. A modern highly qualified specialist should possess communication skills in a foreign language not only at the

household level, but also be able to communicate in the professional sphere, which will make him more competitive both in Uzbek and in the international labor market. That is why a huge number of specialists in the field of economics, business and other branches of professional activity have expressed the need for teaching a foreign language as a tool of professional activity. It should also be noted that in most cases they need a foreign language for everyday communication with foreign colleagues, therefore, the functional, rather than the theoretical aspect of traditional methods of language teaching is put at the forefront. Based on the above, it can be argued that a foreign language at a university acquires the character of a discipline that provides students with a functionally significant means of intercultural communication and cooperation. In the educational practice of teaching a foreign language, there are more and more productive methods and techniques that are due to the development of educational technologies and their introduction into our daily life. These include such as communicative, project, remote techniques that allow you to train all types of speech activity and focused on real communication, and, consequently, meet the needs of students in the current educational situation. The most popular today is, perhaps, the communicative methodology, which is actively being implemented not only in higher education, but also in the system of secondary and primary education. Its advantage is that through a system of diverse exercises and tasks, it is able to eliminate barriers in communication, and therefore make the entire existing language potential of the learner function.

In order to improve the quality of foreign language proficiency and taking into account the limited time frame allocated by the program for its study, some universities are actively implementing subject-language integrated learning (CLIL - Content and Language Integrated Learning). CLIL is interpreted as a teaching method based on mastering a

subject area through a foreign language and a foreign language through a subject. The term CLIL was introduced by D. Marsh and described situations in which all academic disciplines or part of the subjects were taught in a foreign language in order to master the subject and learn a foreign language at the same time. Due to its bi-directionality - subject orientation and foreign language - the CLIL methodology differs significantly from ESP (English for Specific Purposes), which focuses exclusively on the language. It should also be noted that the volume of subject and language content when using this technique can vary significantly both in one direction and in the other, creating so-called content-led and language-led models. In the higher education system in Russia, both models are already being integrated into the educational process, giving preference to the first one due

to objective reasons and an extremely limited amount of contact hours for mastering the subject and a foreign language.

The fundamental principles of the CLIL methodological approach are the following components:

-The subject-content aspect (Content), which provides a wide range of study of the subject, a special terminological base through a foreign language and preparation for further professional activity;

-Social and linguistic aspect (Communication), which creates conditions for the development of communication skills, deeper learning of a foreign language and the opportunity to use acquired competencies for applied purposes;

-Cognitive-learning aspect (Cognition), contributing to the increase of the motivational component of trainees, the development and use of various educational strategies, forms and types of educational activities;

-Cultural aspect (Culture), implying the development of intercultural communication skills, the study and understanding of the peculiarities of culture and relationships of other countries and peoples.

What is the positive potential of integrating CLIL into the educational process for Uzbek educational practice?

Firstly, mastering a subject with the help of a foreign language forms a multidimensional, expanded range of knowledge and skills within the framework of the subject being studied, future profession, activities in the intercultural space, as well as extra-linguistic knowledge - decision-making, teamwork, critical thinking, etc.

Secondly, the very format of classes using the CLIL methodology allows you to get away from monotonously monotonous foreign language classes based on reading, translation of texts and mechanical memorization of a huge amount of vocabulary. Teaching a specialized discipline in a foreign language creates a moment of novelty, which acts as a powerful motivating factor for students, stimulating creative thinking, the ability to adapt to a new situation, willingness to cooperate and language communication. Therefore, it is precisely this technique that will contribute to the development of self-education in a professionally significant and functionally adaptive context. The introduction of the methodology of subject-language integrated learning is sufficient. It successfully takes place abroad (Bulgaria, Finland, Spain, Sweden, Italy) and arouses great interest from teachers and methodologists. Moreover, training by this method is conducted not only in universities, but covers the levels of primary and secondary education in terms of teaching basic school subjects in a non-native language. It is also

noteworthy that the teaching of children using early education methods is based on the perspective of taking into account the functional aspect, i.e. children use language to perform functional tasks.

Thus, the use of an integrated approach to language learning at all levels of education forms a logically structured and conceptually grounded system in which the instrumental value of the language turns into a powerful incentive to master the subject area.

Based on the above and based on the results of the analysis of the situation in universities, it can be concluded that most of the graduates of non-linguistic universities are not able to demonstrate their professional knowledge in a foreign language or maintain communication in a narrow context. This is due to the limited vocabulary, the difficulty of selecting equivalent vocabulary, and the lack of discursive competence to maintain communication. Therefore, it seems absolutely logical to reconsider the existing approaches to language teaching and pay more attention to early language professionalization based on the CLIL methodology, which will bring the educational situation as close as possible to professionally meaningful communication of the business environment.

A comprehensive orientation means the ability to master a language within the framework of non-linguistic subjects and, conversely, to study a subject area in foreign language classes. This approach is based on the principle of integration of several academic disciplines. Subject-language training allows you to work on cross-cultural topics and projects. The creation of a stimulating learning environment involves the use of a system of different types of educational activities within the classroom and, as a result, strengthening students' confidence in the results of educational activities. In addition, it means attracting authentic materials and developing students' language competence.

Authenticity in this case boils down to the fact that students independently signal their language needs. Active learning is reduced to stimulating work in collaboration; teachers acting as mentors and students whose communicative activity prevails in the classroom. Gradual learning involves the revision and restructuring of the student's existing arsenal of skills, interests and experience in more practical formats that meet different learning styles with an emphasis on creativity and critical thinking. Cooperation involves planning lessons together with teachers specializing in the CLIL methodology and subject matter specialists, as well as with the participation of interested representatives of the community and authorities.

The described features of the CLIL model are based on four fundamental principles of the methodology, namely: content, communication, cognition and culture (model 4-C CLI). The practical implementation of CLIL is the result of mental activity, which acts as a mental way of cognition. In CLIL, the focus is on content, not form. Moreover, since meaning formation is both a personal and a social process, new knowledge and skills are developed through personal, as well as joint cognition through a communicative process (communication). There is a large number of research on the implementation of CLIL in the learning process. The theoretical foundations of bilingual education based on content and language integration in a non-linguistic environment are presented in the studies of L. L. Salekhova, K. S. Grigorieva, O. Meyer , F. Ball , D. Coyle , etc . They indicate the following advantages of using CLIL in higher education:

1. Integrated classes increase students' motivation for language learning, since students consider language as a means of studying a specialized subject and obtaining new information. The student's desire to comprehend and use the subject content that encourages him to learn the language.

2. Students have much more opportunities to speak and write about the processes they observe and analyze, which is not only professionally relevant information, but also significantly develops the skills of written communication in a foreign language.

3. Students master the ways of practical application of new knowledge and skills through interactive formats of educational activities.

4. Language learning becomes a powerful tool for expanding professional knowledge and skills.

5. Integrated training contributes to the expansion of career prospects.

6. Students acquire the skills of cooperation, decision-making, teamwork and learn to be independent.

7. The flexibility of this approach makes it possible to easily adapt it to different educational contexts and systems.

We share the point of view of W. Smith, who explains the reasons for the introduction of CLIL in higher education and emphasizes that learning a foreign language as a separate discipline becomes useless in higher education and calls for more attention to be paid to a balanced approach to learning based on professionally oriented content and language integration.

However, the introduction of integration using the CLIL method is not without some difficulties, namely, teaching a subject in a foreign language (economics, management, finance, etc.) can become problematic for teachers of

specialized disciplines, as well as teaching them a foreign language in due volume. On the other hand, teachers of a foreign language are incompetent to present the content of the profile discipline in a foreign language. Consequently, it can be argued that such a universally recognized educational innovation is significantly ahead of the qualitative training of teaching staff who are able to work effectively in an integrated subject-language field. Educational institutions for the training of teachers in many countries do not train specialists for the implementation of CLIL, and the number of available ones is very limited. At the same time, not all specialists are able to focus on the profile content and language goals.

In our opinion, the main attention should be focused on the linguistic training of the teaching staff. At the first stage, it is necessary to determine the existing language skills of teachers, and then develop an individual trajectory of language acquisition, taking into account the required retraining course or improvement of foreign language communicative competence. The developed and proposed English-language online courses, which provide for the active use of the language in the format of group training, will also be useful for language training. For teachers, those who speak a foreign language for teaching a specialized discipline have the opportunity to participate in exchange programs with the status of a visiting professor, which also contributes to the development of language skills. CLIL technology requires significant efforts to organize collaboration and collaboration, and in this sense represent a professional task for both language teachers and teachers of specialized disciplines. Therefore, it is important to draw the attention of the administration of universities to what personnel needs they have they may encounter in the future and how it will be possible to provide the university with such personnel. In order to meet the needs of the teaching staff in improving foreign language skills, some university offers courses to improve foreign language communicative competence for the teaching staff, aimed at educating teachers and supporting them in their desire to develop themselves and their professional qualifications. As practice shows, such an initiative significantly changes the learning process itself: professionally-oriented courses in a foreign language, a new format of classes is being mastered, an exchange of teachers is developing in order to read an author's course of lectures in a foreign language and work within the framework of innovative schemes.

Another problem associated with the implementation of CLIL is the time-consuming and time-consuming preparation for classes, which requires considerable effort to select the content, language and learning skills. For a foreign language teacher, the most problematic may be the selection of the content of the

training session and its adaptation for a specific group students, since such classes require different forms of communication in terms of presenting the material, organizing work with it, developing tasks, etc. Introduction and distribution CLIL technologies contribute to the creation of useful Internet resources that can be useful for both teachers and students.

The process of integrating a foreign language and the subject content of specialized disciplines in a non-linguistic university using the CLIL methodology is undoubtedly an innovation in the system of modern education, as it allows you to cover a very wide range of educational tasks.

The successful implementation of CLIL in the higher school system largely depends on an integrated interdisciplinary approach to the learning process, in which the balance between a foreign language and professionally-oriented content will be to contribute to the formation of the required competencies of future specialists in various sectors of the economy. Therefore, it is important for the CLIL teacher to prioritize such learning activities that develop critical thinking, which focus on task-based learning to increase the level of competence.

REFERENCES:

1. Coyle D., Hood Ph., March D. CLIL: Content and Language Integrated Learning. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2010. 170 p.
2. Mehisto, P., Marsh, D. and Frigols, M. Uncovering CLIL: Content and Language Integrated Learning in Bilingual and Multilingual Education. Oxford: Macmillan, 2008.
3. Meyer O. Introducing the CLIL Pyramid: Key Strategies and Principles for Quality CLIL Planning and Teaching. Basic Issues in EFL-Teaching and Learning, 2010, pp. 11-29.
4. Izomovich, R. Z., & Fazliddinova, U. D. (2022, January). Implications from syntax for teaching a second language. In Integration Conference on Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes (pp. 320-323).
5. Rasulov, Z. (2022). О дискурсивном анализе в современной лингвистике. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz), 25(25).
6. Haydarov, A. A. (2019). METHODOLOGICAL FEATURES OF IMITATION WORDS. Theoretical & Applied Science, (10), 688-690.
7. Askarovich, H. A. (2022). SOME COMMENTS ON THE STYLISTIC REPETITION. JournalNX-A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal, 8 (1), 87-91.

8. Haydarov, A. (2020). Methodological features of graphic tools. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 5.
9. Saidova, Z. (2022). СТРУКТУРНО-ГРАММАТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ПСИХИЧЕСКИХ ПРОЦЕССОВ И ЛИЧНОСТНЫХ СВОЙСТВ КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНАЯ ЗОНА ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЗМ. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. Uz), 8(8).
10. Saidova, Z. (2022). TA'LIM TIZIMIDA MODULYOR OB'YEKTIGA YO'LLANGAN DINAMIK O'QUV MUHITINING (MOODLE) AVTO VA KAMCHLARI. ILMIY NASHRLAR MARKAZI (buxdu.Uz), 8(8). Retrieved from https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/4352.
11. Saidova Zulfizar Khudoyberdievna Questioning techniques in teaching English // Достижения науки и образования. 2018. №5 (27). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/questioning-techniques-in-teaching-english>.
12. Zulfizar Khudoyberdievna, S. . (2022). THE MAIN FEATURES OF TRANSLATION OF PHRASEOLOGY FROM ENGLISH INTO UZBEK. Scientific Impulse, 1(3), 523–526. Retrieved from <https://nauchniyimpuls.ru/index.php/ni/article/view/1024>.
13. Khudoyberdievna, S. Z. (2022, January). Classification of verbal phraseological units denoting the emotional state of a person. In Integration Conference on Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes (pp. 90-93).
14. Saidova, Z. K. (2023). PROBLEMS OF LINGUO-CULTURAL ANALYSIS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 11(2), 700-707. <https://farspublishers.org/index.php/ijessh/article/view/544>.
15. Saidova Zulfizar Khudoyberdievna Implementation of some techniques in developing reading skills in English classes // Достижения науки и образования. 2018. №5 (27). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/implementation-of-some-techniques-in-developing-reading-skills-in-english-classes>.
16. Saidova, Z. X. Implementation of some techniques in developing reading skills in English classes., Достижениянауки и образования № 5 (27) Россия-2018. стр. 59-60.
17. Saidova Zulfizar Khudoyberdievna Model training method: classes in the form of buseness games, lessons such as lesson-court, lesson auction, lesson-press Conference // Достижения науки и образования. 2018. №5 (27). URL:

<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/model-training-method-classes-in-the-form-of-buseness-games-lessons-such-as-lesson-court-lesson-auction-lesson-press-conference>.

18. Saidova, Z. (2022). ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИИ И СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ЕДИНИЦ, ВЫРАЖАЮЩИХ ПСИХИЧЕСКОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ ЧЕЛОВЕКА. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. Uz), 8 (8). ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. Uz), 8(8).

19. Saidova, Z. K. (2023). THE FUNDAMENTAL TYPES OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 11 (2), 517-522.